

Considering collaboration

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

A self-reflective questionnaire on why you would consider participating in the development of a multi-actor project proposal.

Benefits

This questionnaire will help you evaluate whether you are ready and willing to engage in a multi-actor project. It also supports the identification of your own needs and interests and what your own limitations could be within the future multi-actor project.

Practical recommendations

Before deciding upon participation in the development of a project proposal under a call requiring the multi-actor approach, it is important to realise this is not another 'pure science' or 'pure practice' project. A project applying the multi-actor approach, and its related proposal development process, has its own set of advantages and disadvantages, norms and values, and ways of working.

Going through the questionnaire developed by the SHAPE-ID project will help you in gaining a better understanding of both the requirements of engaging in a multi-actor project (in the questionnaire described as an 'interdisciplinary' (ID) or 'transdisciplinary' (TD) collaboration. This is not exactly the same as multi-actor, but has a lot of similar principles) and what you as a partner would like to gain from it.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Work with a diversity of professional backgrounds

Recognize, and work with, the limitations of different organisations

Balance needs of both yourself and the consortium as a whole

Relevant Target groups

All

Useful link(s)*

[SHAPE-ID Reflective tool - Considering collaboration](#)

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